

THE VALUE OF OPTIMAL LOCATION OF AGGLOMERATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGION

Nurbek Toshev Janon o'g'li

Department of Tourism and Marketing, Karshi State University
independent researcher

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Abstract: This article examines the relevance of optimal placement of agglomeration in the development of tourism in the region. Effective management of tourism potential, optimization of infrastructure, rational use of resources and strengthening of tourism interregional cooperation will be covered. As a result of the study, practical recommendations were developed on the geographical location of the agglomeration and its impact on economic efficiency.

Keywords: Tourist agglomerations, optimal placement, economic efficiency, infrastructure, regional development, tourism management.

Introduction. The importance of tourism as an important component of regional development is increasing day by day. In particular, the issue of optimal placement of tourist agglomerations is relevant today, and it contributes greatly to the economic and social development of the region. When placing tourist agglomerations, it is necessary to take into account the natural, cultural and infrastructural potential of the regions, as well as create favorable conditions for meeting the needs of tourists. Proper placement of tourist agglomerations allows not only to increase the quality of tourism services, but also to ensure the economic growth of the regions. In this process, it is important to use local and international experience, as well as to implement innovative solutions. This article analyzes the principles and practices of optimal placement of tourist agglomerations in the region. Also, recommendations for increasing the impact of agglomeration on economic efficiency will be developed.

Development of ecotourism agglomeration infrastructure is relevant in attracting tourists, creating favorable conditions for them and revitalizing the local economy. Through tourists coming to the region, additional funds are injected into the economy, which increases the well-being of the local population. Investments in the field of ecotourism also contribute to the development of the hotel, transport and service sectors. One of the main principles of ecotourism is the preservation of natural resources and their sustainable use. Hisor reserve, mountain landscapes and other ecologically important places in Kashkadarya region require protection. Against the

background of current global climate changes and environmental problems, the importance of protecting natural resources through the establishment of ecotourism infrastructure is increasing. Sustainable development of tourism in Kashkadarya region ensures environmental protection and rational use of resources. By developing ecotourism infrastructure, it is possible to turn the region into an ecologically sustainable region. This allows to minimize the harmful impact on the environment while attracting tourists.

Tourism agglomerationng abroad to study the role of the national economy and the fundamental issues of its development, Romano CA, Tanewski GA, Smyrnios KX Scientific researches of the above-mentioned scientists have their place and importance in the scientific works done in this direction, but the issues related to the role of handicrafts in the field of tourism of the region and the mechanism of development are left out of the scope of research. In the process of researchsystematic approach, logical and comparative methods of analysis,systematic analysis, comparative analysis, monographic analysis, logical and comparative methods of analysis, comprehensive approach, expert assessment,multivariateused methods such as forecasting

Tourist agglomerations serve as an effective means of preserving and popularizing cultural heritage and traditions. This is done by providing tourists with cultural and historical objects, national traditions and heritage located in the tourist agglomeration area. In this process, the restoration and preservation of cultural objects will increase, the local culture and traditions will be recognized internationally, and the local people will participate in the preservation of their cultural heritage and its development through tourism. The organization of tourist agglomerations allows to develop international cooperation and increase the competitiveness of the region. To attract international tourists, the region needs to create and present competitive tourism products. In this process, access to international tourist markets will expand, local services and infrastructure will be adapted to international standards, and the region will be competitive with other tourist centers.

The relevance and importance of the optimal location of the agglomeration in the development of tourism in the region is related to a number of strategic factors, which is of great importance not only in terms of expanding the tourism sector, but also in terms of accelerating economic growth, creating new opportunities for local residents, and protecting the environment. have

By placing agglomeration, combining several tourist objects and creating easy access to them makes the region attractive for tourists. In this process,

through the formation of tourist routes, tourists are given the opportunity to visit several attractions located close to each other. For example, by combining historical and natural zones such as Shahrisabz, Karshi, and Kitab into one touristic cluster, the attractiveness of the area increases.

Effective management of the flow of tourists, through proper placement of tourist agglomerations, the flow of tourists to tourist destinations can be effectively managed. This is done through the following aspects. Regulation of the flow, directing the flow of tourists to several destinations prevents overloading of attractions and contributes to their stable operation. Optimum placement will reduce the problems associated with seasonal tourism and attract tourists throughout the year.

By not harming the environment, agglomerations ensure environmental sustainability and reduce overuse of natural resources. Local population participation, through sustainable development, active participation of local population in tourism projects is encouraged, which leads to socio-economic growth. Optimum placement of agglomeration in the development of tourism in the region is an important strategy for effective management of tourism and its sustainable development. It not only supports economic growth, but also serves to preserve cultural heritage, rational use of natural resources, and create a favorable tourist environment for tourists. By implementing this process in Kashkadarya region, it is possible to create wide opportunities for international and local tourists. Here is a concept map for ecological tourism depicting Hisar Mountains, Guzor and Kitab Reserves and Aksuv Valley. It highlights key features such as mountain ranges, reserves and river valleys. It is important to place agglomerations based on the location of natural resources for the development of ecotourism. This, on the one hand, ensures the protection of the environment, and on the other hand, increases the attraction of tourists. The objective need for the optimal location of the tourist agglomeration in Kashkadarya region depends on several main factors, which is important for the effective implementation of the tourism potential of the region, economic development and employment of the population. Kashkadarya region, especially the city of Shahrisabz, has a rich cultural and historical heritage. Monuments of Amir Temur and Timurid era, such as Aksaroy, Dorut-Tilovat and Dorut-Saodat ensembles, are of great interest to international tourists. Therefore, there is a need to manage the flow of tourists and more effectively promote the attractions through several regions by properly managing the Historical Heritage and connecting them to each other and placing them in the agglomeration. Natural

resources and ecological tourism opportunities, Kashkadarya region is famous for its natural resources and beautiful mountain scenery. Hisar Mountains, Guzor and Kitab Reserve, Aksuv Valley have great potential for the development of ecological tourism. These areas should be turned into tourist objects while maintaining ecological stability.

It is difficult to reach some ecotourism areas of Kashkadarya region, especially mountainous and rural areas. The low quality of road networks and the lack of modern transport infrastructure limit the flow of tourists. Development of road and transport networks, creation of convenient transport connections to the main tourist centers of the region. Ecotourism infrastructure (hotels, camping sites, recreation centers) is not sufficiently developed. There is a lack of convenient conditions and service points for tourists. Attracting investments in ecotourism infrastructure, expanding the scope of tourist services by establishing small hotels and resorts. Environmental norms and standards are often not followed in projects related to ecotourism. This can lead to pollution or damage to natural resources in the area. Development of infrastructure based on the principles of sustainable tourism and implementation of a strict environmental control system aimed at protecting natural resources. There is insufficient information about ecotourism sites and tourism opportunities in the province. This makes it difficult to attract the attention of local and foreign tourists. It is necessary to introduce modern marketing strategies, to spread information about the ecotourism opportunities of the region on digital platforms and social networks. Lack of an effective system for management and development of ecotourism. Cooperation between local government bodies and the private sector is insufficient. Greater cooperation between local governments, the private sector and foreign investors in tourism development is needed.

Conclusions and suggestions. The following conclusions and proposals were developed for the optimal placement of tourist agglomerations in the development of tourism in the region. Optimal placement of tourist agglomerations serves to maximize the tourism potential of the regions. The correct choice of location strategy is necessary to increase economic efficiency and improve the quality of tourist services. Development of infrastructure and rational use of resources ensure the successful operation of tourist agglomerations. Development of strategies for the placement of tourist agglomerations taking into account geographical and economic factors. Modernization of tourism infrastructure and creation of amenities for tourists.

Increasing tourism flows through the development of interregional and international cooperation. Improving the management system of tourist agglomerations and introducing innovative technologies. Development of the regional economy by involving local residents and entrepreneurs in tourism projects

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